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School Accountability and Teachers' Grading in a Low-Stakes System: Evidence from a Randomized Monitoring Experiment in Italy

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of a large-scale randomized repeated external monitoring program on teachers' grading practices in a low-stakes accountability system. We leverage the repeated random assignment of external monitors in Italian primary schools between 2012 and 2015 to estimate the causal effects of this accountability tool on school-level grading. Drawing on comprehensive administrative data (INVALSI-SNV) covering the universe of fifth-grade students, we employ a staggered difference-in-differences design to estimate short- and medium-term effects on average grades and grading standards. Our analysis reveals that the monitoring program has no measurable impact on teachers' grading practices. These findings suggest that grading - an entrenched and locally governed pedagogical practice - remains largely unaffected by episodic external monitoring when embedded in a low-stakes context. More broadly, the study highlights the limits of soft accountability mechanisms in shaping professional norms and reducing grading disparities in education systems without formal performance-based incentives.

Keywords: accountability policies, accountability pressures, grading practices, grade deflation, Italian education system, external monitors.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, education systems across the globe have embraced accountability reforms aimed at improving school performance, reducing inequalities, and fostering transparency. These reforms often rely on standardized assessments and external evaluations to realign school practices with national policy goals and public expectations. From the United States to Europe and beyond, accountability policies have emerged as key instruments to address the so-called principal-agent problem in education, where teachers and schools may not naturally align with the interests of policymakers or the public (Grossman and Hart, 1983; Figlio and Loeb, 2011).

In the United States, the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) Act and subsequent policies introduced high-stakes accountability mechanisms, linking test results to funding decisions, sanctions, and public reporting. These reforms have been associated with modest improvements in student achievement (Carnoy and Loeb, 2002; Hanushek and Raymond, 2005), but also with significant unintended consequences such as curriculum narrowing, teaching to the test, and various forms of strategic behavior (Jacob and Levitt, 2003; Jennings et al., 2014).

In contrast, other countries - including several in Europe - have implemented low-stakes accountability systems. In these systems, standardized assessments are used primarily for diagnostic and informational purposes, without direct consequences for students, teachers, or schools. Italy offers a prime example of this softer model of accountability, where external evaluations are formally decoupled from resource allocation, career advancement, or school sanctions. While the results of Italy's National Evaluation Program (SNV), implemented by the INVALSI institute, are not tied to formal rewards or penalties, they nonetheless generate informal pressures. Media coverage, parental school choice, and inter-school comparisons contribute to reputational accountability for school leaders and staff (Lucifora and Tonello, 2020).

Despite their more benign institutional design, low-stakes systems may still shape school behavior through mechanisms such as social norms, peer comparison, and perceived surveillance. In Italy, for example, strategic responses have been observed even in the absence of formal sanctions, including the manipulation of student test participation and teaching to the test (Jäger et al., 2012; Lucifora and Tonello, 2020). One policy response has been the introduction of external monitors, randomly assigned to oversee standardized testing in a subsample of classes. These monitors aim to curb cheating and increase the credibility of test

results, especially in areas where trust in central education authorities and civic capital are low (Paccagnella and Sestito, 2014; Ferrer-Esteban and Pagès, 2024).

While the literature on school accountability has largely focused on test score outcomes, much less is known about how these policies influence teachers' everyday pedagogical practices, such as grading. Yet grades remain a key mechanism for student evaluation, signaling, and selection, particularly in systems like Italy's, where they can shape access to academic tracks and long-term educational trajectories (Chowdhury, 2018; Lievore, Fedeli & Triventi, 2024). Grading is also more opaque and locally governed than standardized testing, often embedded in routine practices and long-standing professional cultures (Dardanoni, Monica & Pennisi, 2010; Triventi & Argentin, 2015).

In this study, we examine whether the temporary presence of external monitors during national standardized assessments affects teachers' grading behavior in subsequent years. We leverage the repeated random assignment of monitors across Italian primary schools to identify causal effects on two key outcomes: average grades and grading standards. Our hypothesis is that exposure to external monitoring could lead to grade deflation due to changes in teachers' beliefs about evaluation norms, informal convergence toward stricter grading standards among teaching staff, or reputational concerns vis-à-vis school leaders or external evaluators.

By focusing on grading practices within a low-stakes accountability regime, this study contributes to a broader understanding of how external pressures interact with deeply embedded educational routines. It also expands existing accountability research beyond the U.S. context, offering comparative insights into when and how accountability can (or cannot) shape internal school processes.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the monitoring program in the context of the Italian accountability system. Section 3 reviews the international literature on accountability and its effects on teaching and grading, examining evidence from the Italian context. Section 4 outlines the theoretical framework and elaborates on the hypothesis and underlying mechanisms. Section 5 describes the data and methodology. Section 6 presents the results, focusing on the heterogeneity of the effects. Sections 7 and 8 discuss the main findings and outline the principal limitations, while Section 9 draws the conclusions.

2. The Italian External Monitoring Program and Accountability System

2.1. Accountability in a Low-Stakes System

Italy represents a valuable case for analyzing the effects of accountability policies in a low-stakes educational context, where formal consequences for performance are minimal or absent. Unlike high-stakes systems such as those in the United States or England - where student achievement on standardized tests can influence school funding, teacher contracts, or school closures - the Italian system is designed around diagnostic and informational accountability (Bovens, 2007; Verger and Parcerisa, 2017). The national testing program, developed by INVALSI (the National Institute for the Evaluation of the Education and Training System), serves to monitor educational outcomes and provide schools with comparative performance feedback, but it does not directly determine access to resources or personnel decisions.

Although INVALSI results are not tied to incentives or sanctions, the accountability system has acquired symbolic and reputational value over time. Media reporting, local rankings, and parental school choice have contributed to making standardized test results more salient to schools and principals (Lucifora and Tonello, 2020). As such, Italian accountability policies generate indirect performance pressures that can lead to strategic responses - even in the absence of explicit stakes - highlighting the need to examine behavioral effects under these softer accountability conditions.

The combination of diagnostic accountability and elements typically associated with high-stakes environments, such as media coverage, local rankings, and parental choice, suggests that the boundaries between high- and low-stakes systems may be blurred. Nonetheless, we argue that the design of the Italian national standardized assessment is intended to remain low-stakes. As outlined in the INVALSI statute (Ministry of Education and Research Decree No. 11-2011), the evaluation aims to provide the central government with a comprehensive overview of the school system's performance and to offer schools a standardized benchmark for self-assessing their strengths and weaknesses.

2.2. The National Evaluation Program and External Monitoring

Since the 2009-10 academic year, INVALSI has conducted annual standardized tests across a national census of students in grades 2, 5, 8, 10, and 13. Students are assessed in Italian language and mathematics, and, starting in later years, English and civic education. These tests are externally developed, centrally administered, and not used for student tracking or certification, but they serve as reference benchmarks for schools' self-evaluation.

To address concerns about cheating and ensure the credibility of test administration, INVALSI introduced an external monitoring program. Each year, a sample of schools is randomly selected - using a two-stage, regionally stratified design - and assigned external monitors drawn from a national pool of retired teachers and principals. These monitors oversee test administration procedures and verify compliance with testing protocols.

Specifically, they are required to perform the following tasks in the sampled classrooms: (i) supervise students during the tests, (ii) provide detailed information regarding the test administration, and (iii) calculate the test scores and submit the results and accompanying documentation to INVALSI within a few days (INVALSI, 2010).

The randomization procedure ensures plausibly exogenous variation in exposure to external supervision, creating a natural experiment that we exploit in our empirical strategy.

Monitors are assigned at the class level, but in practice their presence can trigger school-level responses. Principals may assign stronger or more compliant classes to be tested, or teachers may adjust attendance or preparation strategies in anticipation of scrutiny (Lucifora and Tonello, 2020). The limited advance notice - just a few days before testing - serves to reduce preemptive manipulations, although some reactive behaviors remain possible.

2.3. Why Italy? Educational Stratification, Regional Inequalities, and Grading Autonomy

Three structural features of the Italian school system make it particularly relevant for studying how low-stakes accountability interacts with entrenched educational practices such as grading. First, regional inequalities in school performance and grading standards are deeply rooted and well-documented. The North-South divide, long studied in relation to civic capital and institutional trust (Putnam et al., 1993), extends to the education system, with Southern regions showing lower standardized test scores but more generous grading (Dardanoni, Modica & Pennisi, 2010; Triventi and Argentin, 2015). These disparities raise the question of whether external accountability pressures have differential effects depending on regional culture, norms, and expectations.

Second, schools enjoy considerable autonomy in grading, with few national guidelines beyond the use of a 1-to-10 scale. While grades are not determinative for formal progression at the primary level, they play a crucial signaling role for families, particularly at key educational transitions such as the end of primary school (Contini and Triventi, 2016). In this decentralized environment, grading norms develop at the school level and are heavily influenced by local

pedagogical cultures, making them potentially resistant to external change, but also subject to internal redefinition under new pressures.

Third, the Italian school system is marked by significant heterogeneity in school size and socioeconomic composition. Larger schools, often located in urban areas, may be more bureaucratically structured and exposed to public scrutiny, which could amplify the informal stakes of external monitoring. Similarly, schools with higher socioeconomic status (SES) student populations may operate under stronger normative expectations around rigor, performance, and alignment with standardized metrics. Conversely, schools serving more disadvantaged communities may see accountability as externally imposed and less relevant to their everyday functioning (Ferrer-Esteban and Pagès, 2024).

These structural differences suggest that the effects of accountability policies, even under low-stakes conditions, may vary along key institutional dimensions. In our empirical analysis, we therefore examine treatment heterogeneity by geographic macro-area (North vs. Center-South), school size, and average school-level SES, to better understand how institutional context shapes school-level responses to external monitoring.

3. Literature Review

3.1. International Evidence on Accountability and Its Effects on Teaching and Grading

Over the past two decades, a large body of research - particularly from the United States - has examined how accountability reforms influence school behavior. These studies generally focus on high-stakes accountability systems, where standardized test results are tied to funding, sanctions, public reporting, or even school closures. Early research suggested that such accountability regimes can yield positive effects on student achievement (Carnoy and Loeb, 2002; Hanushek and Raymond, 2005; Figlio and Loeb, 2011), but also generate perverse incentives that alter school and teacher behavior.

Perhaps the most widely studied unintended consequence is “teaching to the test,” where instructional time is disproportionately devoted to test-related content, narrowing the curriculum and limiting broader educational aims (Jennings and Bearak, 2014; Koretz, 2017). Other studies document strategic behavior by teachers and administrators, including outright

cheating, reclassification of students as special needs, or test-day exclusions to manipulate score distributions (Jacob and Levitt, 2003; Jacob, 2005).

Importantly, recent research has turned attention to how accountability affects teachers' grading practices, an area with direct implications for equity and instructional integrity. Studies from the U.S. suggest that teachers may inflate classroom grades in response to external test pressures - particularly in untested subjects or years - to compensate for performance expectations or protect student morale (Mittleman and Jennings, 2018). Such strategic grading has been shown to vary across schools and student populations, reflecting broader inequalities in institutional environments and accountability salience.

Outside the U.S., scholars have identified similar dynamics in systems with varying degrees of accountability pressure. In Germany, Jäger et al. (2012) found evidence of test-oriented instruction even in relatively low-stakes settings. In Ontario (Canada), Ohemeng and McCall-Thomas (2013) reported unintended behaviors in schools driven by accountability-based performance management. These findings suggest that even in low-stakes systems, accountability tools can alter teacher behavior, but their reach and permanence may depend on how deeply they challenge existing professional norms and institutional routines.

Despite this growing literature, empirical studies on the relationship between accountability and grading in low-stakes settings remain scarce, especially those using causal identification strategies. This gap is particularly notable given that grades, unlike test scores, often serve as the primary signal for student ability, progress, and placement in education systems with significant within-country stratification.

3.2. Evidence from the Italian Context

The Italian system has been the focus of a growing number of studies since the introduction of the INVALSI testing regime and its external monitoring program. Several papers have leveraged the randomized assignment of external monitors to estimate the program's impact on cheating and test manipulation. Angrist et al. (2014) and Lucifora and Tonello (2015) provide robust evidence that external monitors reduce test score inflation, especially in schools located in Southern Italy and in classes with low-performing students.

Further studies have shown that the effects of external monitoring are heterogeneous. For instance, Bertoni et al. (2013) and Bertoni et al. (2019) report stronger effects in schools with smaller class sizes and a higher share of tenured teachers. The effectiveness of monitoring also

varies by geography and school-level civic capital (Paccagnella and Sestito, 2014), with greater manipulation observed in low-trust environments, supporting a cultural-institutional interpretation of opportunistic behavior in response to accountability.

There is also evidence of spillover effects, with unmonitored classes within the same school showing signs of behavioral change after their peers are monitored (Bertoni et al., 2013). These school-level effects suggest that teachers adapt to perceived norms or reputational pressures even when not directly exposed to monitoring. The behavioral impact, however, appears to be short-lived: Bertoni et al. (2021) find that effects on test outcomes vanish two years after the treatment, pointing to weak institutionalization of accountability norms.

While this literature has significantly advanced our understanding of test-related behaviors, very little is known about how external monitoring influences grading practices, which are often governed by internal school norms and individual discretion rather than centralized control. This is a critical gap, particularly in Italy, where grading is decentralized, highly variable across regions and schools, and has strong implications for students' future educational trajectories (Triventi and Argentin, 2015; Lievore, Fedeli & Triventi, 2024).

By investigating how external monitoring affects grading behavior, our study expands the literature beyond test performance to consider how accountability mechanisms interact with long-standing, routinized pedagogical practices. In doing so, we also aim to explore how institutional, geographical, and social contexts condition the effects of accountability even in a low-stakes setting.

4. Theoretical Framework

The implementation of accountability policies is often premised on the assumption that external performance pressures will translate into improved teaching and learning. However, the mechanisms through which these pressures affect teachers' everyday practices are far from straightforward. While most empirical research has focused on the impact of accountability on standardized test performance, there is increasing interest in understanding how such policies shape less-visible but equally consequential practices, such as grading.

Grading is a deeply embedded aspect of school life. It plays a critical role not only in shaping students' self-perception and motivation, but also in signaling academic potential to families and guiding placement into differentiated educational tracks. In contexts like Italy, where grades influence upper secondary school choice, these practices carry substantial weight in

reproducing social and educational inequalities (Contini and Triventi, 2016; Lievore et al., 2024). Yet grading is also a highly localized and autonomous process. Teachers develop their own evaluative standards, often informally and in interaction with school culture and peer norms. This embeddedness may render grading less responsive to external pressures than more standardized, externally monitored procedures.

The introduction of external accountability mechanisms may disrupt these routines. Drawing on sociological and organizational theories, accountability can be seen as a symbolic and regulatory intervention that redefines professional expectations and introduces new reference points for evaluation (Day, 2002; Verger and Parcerisa, 2017). Even in low-stakes accountability systems, where performance data are not linked to sanctions or rewards, schools and teachers may still perceive reputational risks associated with underperformance or inconsistency between grades and test scores. Such pressures may encourage strategic adaptation, particularly when they challenge the legitimacy or credibility of existing internal standards.

Ethnographic and qualitative research has long emphasized how accountability reforms reshape teachers' professional identities, leading to intensified workloads, reduced autonomy, and increased administrative expectations (Sloan, 2006; Jeffrey, 2002; Katsuno, 2012). These shifts may be experienced as externally imposed and misaligned with teachers' pedagogical values, generating ambivalence or resistance. Yet other accounts stress the adaptive capacity of educators, who may negotiate and reinterpret accountability requirements through professional dialogue and shared reflection (Darling-Hammond, 2004; Whitty, 2002). Accountability, then, is not merely a constraint but a structuring force, one that can be refracted through existing school cultures and teacher communities in diverse ways.

Building on these insights, we focus on whether exposure to external monitoring - as a concrete instantiation of accountability - affects subsequent grading practices in Italian primary schools. We hypothesize that exposure to external monitors leads to a subsequent *grade deflation* at the school level. We identified three potential mechanisms through which a negative delayed effect may arise.

1) *Norm Internalization*: Exposure to external monitoring may prompt individual teachers to reconsider their own evaluative standards, especially when the experience highlights a mismatch between internal grading practices and external performance expectations. Teachers may adopt more conservative or standardized grading criteria, perceiving the monitoring episode as a cue to align with national norms (Ferretti et al., 2020).

2) *Social Norm Negotiation*: Rather than acting in isolation, teachers may engage in collective sensemaking following monitoring, leading to the informal establishment of stricter internal norms for grading. In this view, external pressure catalyzes internal professional deliberation, encouraging convergence around more defensible and uniform evaluative standards (Whitty, 2002).

3) *Reputational Alignment*: Teachers may fear that large discrepancies between test scores and assigned grades could attract scrutiny or reflect poorly on their professionalism. Even in the absence of formal consequences, perceived reputational risks - especially in schools with a visible public profile or active parental communities - may lead teachers to adjust grades downward to pre-empt critique from principals, peers, or external evaluators (Bertoni et al., 2013; Verger and Parcerisa, 2017).

These mechanisms may operate unevenly across contexts. Schools differ in their organizational structure, peer cultures, and exposure to external pressures. We therefore expect heterogeneity in the effects of monitoring across several dimensions. Considering the geographic context, in Southern Italy, where civic capital is lower and opportunistic behavior in response to accountability has been more frequent (Paccagnella and Sestito, 2014), teachers may perceive monitoring as more intrusive or illegitimate, potentially leading to stronger defensive reactions or symbolic compliance. A second potential moderator is school size: larger schools may be more exposed to public scrutiny and more formalized in their administrative routines, potentially making them more sensitive to external signals. Finally, schools' socioeconomic composition might play a role as well: schools with higher-SES student bodies may face greater reputational stakes and stronger expectations around rigor, thus being more responsive to subtle accountability cues. Conversely, disadvantaged schools may prioritize internal cohesion or pedagogical autonomy over perceived external alignment.

Overall, we hypothesize that external monitoring will lead to modest, delayed reductions in average grades and grading leniency, particularly in schools where informal accountability pressures are more salient. However, we also anticipate that effects will be limited in magnitude and short-lived, given the path-dependent and deeply embedded nature of grading practices.

We argue that, although the monitoring event constitutes an episodic disruption in school life, it remains theoretically plausible to expect an impact on everyday pedagogical routines. Indeed, despite its brevity and lack of formal evaluative consequences, the monitoring may function as a symbolic intervention, signaling expectations regarding assessment rigor and alignment with standardized benchmarks. Specifically, we expect that the effects may be primarily driven by mechanisms of reputational alignment. During the period under consideration - corresponding

to the initial introduction of standardized assessments in Italy - there was widespread concern among teachers that they might eventually be evaluated based on students' performance in the INVALSI tests (Lucifora and Tonello, 2019). Moreover, the monitors' responsibilities extend beyond overseeing the test administration to include the correction of the tests and the calculation of scores, a process that introduces elements associated to evaluative roles. Taken together, these elements contribute to substantiate the theoretical plausibility of an effect that can be open to empirical investigation.

5. Data and Methods

5.1 Data

For this study, we leverage the repeated random assignment of external monitors from the 2012-2013 to 2014-2015 scholastic years. The INVALSI data used in our analysis cover the entire population of Italian students in 5th grade.

The decision to restrict the sample to 5th grade students relies on the assumption that that represents a critical point in students' educational trajectories. In the final year of elementary school (*scuola elementare*) grades play a pivotal signaling role, marking the transition to the next level of education. It is relevant to highlight that, in Italy, while grades do not formally determine access to the next educational level, they strongly influence parental decisions when choosing their children's educational trajectories (Contini and Triventi, 2016; Argentin et al., 2017).

Following Bertoni and colleagues (2019) we exclude from the sample school institutes located in Trentino and Valle d'Aosta, two regions that decided to assign all their classes to external monitors. Next, we exclude classes with fewer than 10 enrolled students, as these are often multi-grade classes. Additionally, we omit schools with fewer than 10 enrolled students in the grade for any given year, as these are not included in the sampling process for external monitors. The decision to aggregate student-level data at the school level is motivated by several methodological considerations: i) potential deviations from true randomness in the class-level assignment of the treatment (Lucifora and Tonello, 2020); ii) documented evidence of spillover effects from monitored to unmonitored classes within the same school (Bertoni et al., 2013); and iii) the analytical focus of this study on school-level grading practices, rather than individual or classroom dynamics.

The analytical sample thus comprises 1,494,688 students nested within 15,418 schools; specifically, 14,414 schools in 2012, 14,222 in 2013, and 12,710 in 2014. Among the 15,418 schools included in the dataset, 75.6% ($n = 11,650$) appear in all three years of observation; 14.9% ($n = 2,293$) appear in two consecutive years, while the remaining fraction is observed in just one year. This unbalancedness stems from both school closures and administrative restructuring over the study period. Despite this variation in panel completeness, the substantial proportion of units with full coverage ensures sufficient longitudinal variation to support the identification strategy.

5.2 Variables

In Italy, students are graded on a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 represents the lowest score, 10 the highest, and 6 is the minimum passing grade. At the end of the academic year, report cards are shared with parents. If a student receives a mark below 6 in any subject, they must take a remedial exam (*esame di riparazione*) in that subject before the new school year starts in September. If they fail the exam, they are required to repeat the year. For cases where students have grades below 6 in three or more subjects, the decision to advance is made collectively by the group of teachers (*Consiglio di classe*). The grading process grants significant autonomy to teachers, who establish their own grading criteria mostly according to each school's specific regulation (Lievore et al., 2024).

To measure grades, we rely on the written mark, substituting it with the oral mark when the written one is missing. This preference for written marks aligns with the fact that also the tests in the years under consideration were administered in a paper-and-pencil format (Triventi and Argentin, 2015).

We include oral marks in our analysis due to the high correlation between the two types of assessments (see Table A.1 in the Appendix). This correlation is likely due to the common practice in primary and lower secondary schools of assigning identical marks for written and oral assessments, rather than evaluating them separately (Triventi and Argentin, 2015).

In addition to average marks, we examine a second outcome: grading standards. To measure grading standards at the school level, we calculate residuals from a linear regression model in which grades are regressed on standardized test scores (including a quadratic term) and key sociodemographic covariates, namely school-level socio-economic background, the proportion of native students, the proportion of female students.

Schools with higher residuals assign average grades that exceed what would be predicted based on their students' performance in national standardized assessments, indicating more generous grading standards. Conversely, schools with lower residuals assign grades that fall below expectations based on test scores, suggesting stricter or more conservative grading practices. The stratifying variables used in the analysis include macro-regions, as defined by the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT); school size, proxied by the number of students participating in the test; and school-level ESCS, an index of students' socio-economic background provided by INVALSI and standardized to have a mean of zero.

5.3 Estimation methods

To estimate the causal effects of external monitoring, we adopt an event-study approach that extends a staggered difference-in-differences framework. This methodology takes advantage of the staggered timing of treatment adoption, allowing us to identify both leads and lags relative to the treatment. By visually inspecting the event study plot, we can assess the magnitude and variability of the estimated coefficients for each period; we expect to observe no significant trends prior to treatment, consistent with the identifying assumptions of the event study design, and hypothesize that negative effects are likely to emerge following exposure to monitoring.

The model takes the following form:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \delta_t + \sum\{k \neq 0\} \beta_k \cdot D_{it}^k + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where Y_{it} is the outcome of interest for school i at time t ; α_i captures school fixed effects; δ_t captures year fixed effects; D_{it}^k is a dummy equal to 1 if school i is k periods away from treatment at time t (excluding $k = 0$, which serves as the reference period); β_k measures the effect of treatment at each relative time k ; and ε_{it} is the error term. By controlling for school fixed effects and year dummies, we are more able to effectively isolate the causal effect from time-invariant, school-specific unobserved factors and common trends in grading practices that affect all schools.

It is important to note that this specification differs from the one used by Bertoni and colleagues (2021), who accounted for the INVALSI randomization protocol and included both region-by-year dummies and their interactions with school size in a lagged dynamic model. We argue

that, given our focus on school grading practices, controlling for school fixed effects within a differences-in-differences framework is a more appropriate approach.

To account for the hierarchical structure of the data, standard errors are clustered at the school level, thereby adjusting for within-school correlation over time. They are computed using the wild bootstrap method to ensure robustness in the presence of heteroskedasticity and a limited number of clusters.

Among the schools in our dataset, 335 received the treatment in more than one year. In these cases, we consider only the *first year* in which the school received the treatment for the purpose of identification.

From a theoretical standpoint, the first exposure to the policy is likely to generate the largest behavioral response, as it typically initiates organizational change; additional treatments in subsequent years may reinforce or sustain these effects.

From an econometric perspective, retaining only the first treatment allows us to avoid complications arising from staggered adoption designs, where units are treated at different times and may also contribute to both the treated and control groups at different points in time. Recent work (e.g., de Chaisemartin & D’Haultfœuille, 2020) has shown that standard two-way fixed effects estimators can produce biased estimates in such settings, particularly when treatment effects are heterogeneous over time or across units.

By focusing on the first treatment year, we define a single treatment cohort per school and improve interpretability, mitigating issues related to treatment reversals and multiple switches.

6. Empirical findings

6.1 Descriptive Statistics

To assess the presence of systematic differences between monitored and unmonitored schools, we present a balance table for each year with available information on the treatment variable. The balance tables for the scholastic year 2013-2014 and 2014-2015 can be found in the Appendix (Table A.2 and Table A.3).

At baseline, no significant differences in mean marks are observed between 5th grade students in the treatment and control group. In the treated schools, as anticipated by previous literature (Bertoni et al., 2021; Lucifora and Tonello, 2020), INVALSI scores are systematically lower

compared to unmonitored schools. Additionally, the standard deviation is smaller, suggesting that external monitoring reduces the dispersion of test scores within the sampled schools. The average school size is larger in the treatment group, a difference that stems from the sampling design, in which the probability of selection is proportional to the number of students taking the test.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of unmonitored and monitored schools (2012).

Variable	Unmonitored	Monitored	Total	Test
N	13448 (93.3%)	966 (6.7%)	14414 (100%)	
Grades				
Mean - Italian	7.66 (0.55)	7.70 (0.59)	7.66 (0.55)	0.02
Mean - Math	7.73 (0.58)	7.78 (0.60)	7.73 (0.58)	0.03
CV - Italian	0.13 (0.03)	0.13 (0.03)	0.13 (0.03)	0.38
CV - Math	0.14 (0.03)	0.14 (0.03)	0.14 (0.03)	0.57
INVALSI Scores				
Mean - Italian	207.29 (20.57)	200.73 (15.87)	206.85 (20.36)	<.001
Mean - Math	210.84 (24.07)	201.78 (18.55)	210.24 (23.84)	<.001
CV - Italian	0.17 (0.04)	0.19 (0.04)	0.18 (0.04)	<.001
CV - Math	0.17 (0.04)	0.18 (0.03)	0.17 (0.04)	<.001
School characteristics				
School size	36.22 (24.72)	47.48 (29.56)	36.98 (25.23)	<.001
Female	0.50 (0.12)	0.50 (0.10)	0.50 (0.11)	0.89
Natives	0.90 (0.12)	0.89 (0.15)	0.90 (0.12)	<.001
School-level ESCS	-0.02 (0.52)	-0.01 (0.47)	-0.02 (0.51)	0.73

Note. Values are means with standard deviations in parentheses. CV = coefficient of variation. ESCS = index of economic, social, and cultural status provided by INVALSI and standardized to a mean of zero. The *Test* column reports *p*-values from *t*-tests comparing monitored and unmonitored schools.

6.2 *The effect of the external monitoring on teachers' grading*

The event study plots display estimated treatment effects with 95% confidence intervals over a four-year window surrounding the intervention. The vertical dashed line at $t = 0$ marks the onset of treatment, defined as the year in which the school is first exposed to external monitoring. The horizontal red line indicates the zero-effect benchmark, against which deviations in estimated effects are interpreted. We expect to observe no significant trends in the two years preceding treatment, consistent with the identifying assumptions of the event study design, and hypothesize the emergence of delayed negative effects in the two years following exposure.

First, we present the event study plots with the main outcomes, marks (Figure 1) and grading standards (Figure 2) both in Italian and Math.

To explore potential heterogeneity in the effects, we then estimated the same model separately for regions in Northern Italy and those in Central and Southern Italy, grouping the North-West with the North-East, and combining the Center, South, and Islands into a single category, following ISTAT classification (Figure 3 and 4). Then, in order to assess whether school size moderates the impact of external monitoring, we present event study plots stratified by school size: Figures 5 and 6 compare schools in the first quartile of the distribution with those in the second quartile. Finally, in Figure A.1 and A.2 the heterogeneous effects are estimated in relation to schools' socioeconomic background by stratifying the analysis according to school-level ESCS and comparing schools in the first quartile with schools in the second.

The event study plots suggest that external monitoring has no statistically significant impact on student outcomes in either Italian or Mathematics. Across all estimated coefficients the confidence intervals consistently overlap with zero. This pattern indicates the absence of detectable effects on both average marks and grading standards following the implementation of monitoring, providing no evidence of either anticipatory responses or delayed impacts.

As robustness checks, we replicated the analysis focusing on grade 8, the second stage in a student's educational trajectory where grades serve a signaling function, especially in the transition to upper secondary education. The results, not shown for brevity, align with those for grade 5: no detectable effects and no evidence of heterogeneity across schools. Moreover, employing the estimator developed by de Chaisemartin and D'Haultfœuille (2020), which accounts for treatment effect heterogeneity in staggered rollout designs, we found no significant impact on either average grades or grading standards.

Finally, additional analyses using the coefficient of variation in student marks as the outcome variable reveal no effect on within-school dispersion of grades.

Figure 1. The effect of external monitoring on marks.

Figure 2. The effect of external monitoring on grading standards.

Figure 3. North vs Center-South: the effect of external monitoring on marks.

Figure 4. North vs Center-South: the effect of external monitoring on grading standards.

Figure 5. Large vs small schools: the effect of external monitoring on marks.

Figure 6. Large vs small schools: the effect of external monitoring on grading standards.

7. Discussion

Accountability policies are more central than ever in the education debate and are part of the policy recommendations of numerous international organizations, such as the World Bank, the OECD, and UNESCO. Nonetheless, accountability remains a contested and multifaceted concept, often interpreted in different ways by various actors (Bovens, 2007; West et al., 2011). While the standardized, test-based accountability model has become dominant globally, its implementation varies considerably across national systems.

In high-stakes contexts - as exemplified by the United States or England - standardized test results are directly tied to financial incentives, teacher evaluations, and school sanctions. These regimes have been associated with modest gains in student achievement (Carnoy and Loeb, 2002; Hanushek and Raymond, 2005; Figlio and Loeb, 2011), but also with unintended consequences, including teaching to the test, curriculum narrowing, and strategic behavior by educators (Jacob and Levitt, 2003; Jennings and Bearak, 2014; Ohemeng and McCall-Thomas, 2013).

By contrast, low-stakes accountability systems - such as the Italian one - rely on diagnostic tools and symbolic pressures, where performance information is collected and disseminated but not directly linked to funding, staffing, or progression decisions. Nonetheless, the promotion of accountability instruments has faced strong resistance from the teachers and teachers' unions. While such systems are expected to foster self-reflection and internal improvement, their ability to alter deeply rooted school practices remains an open question.

Drawing on Verger and Parcerisa's (2017) call to open the "black box" of school responses to accountability, we shift attention from test scores to teachers' grading practices, an area that remains largely understudied in this literature. Specifically, we examine whether the temporary presence of external monitors - a key deterrence mechanism introduced in Italy's National Evaluation Program (SNV) - affects school-level grading patterns in primary and lower secondary education.

Contrary to our theoretical expectations, the analysis does not reveal any measurable effect of external monitoring on either grades or grading standards. Estimated effects are consistently close to zero, with confidence intervals crossing the null and effect sizes well below conventional thresholds of relevance. Although school size and regional context were considered as potential moderators, the results indicate a remarkably uniform absence of impact across the population of schools.

These findings align with the idea that grading is a path-dependent and routinized practice (Day, 2002), shaped by professional cultures, collegial norms, and local interpretations of student performance (Ferretti et al., 2020; Whitty, 2002). In Italy, teachers exercise considerable autonomy in assigning marks, and grading often reflects a school's internal logic more than external benchmarks. As Lievore, Fedeli, and Triventi (2024) show, differences in grading standards can have meaningful long-term consequences for students' academic trajectories, especially in a system where marks influence access to more prestigious academic tracks. Yet our results suggest that short-term accountability cues - such as a one-off monitoring intervention - are insufficient to shift such practices, particularly in the absence of formal incentives or structural follow-up.

One possible explanation is that teachers do not perceive the monitoring event as a signal for broader change, but rather as a procedural requirement tied specifically to the administration of INVALSI tests. Whereas cheating on tests or manipulating attendance are clearly linked to test-day performance (Lucifora and Tonello, 2015; Bertoni et al., 2013), grading is embedded in a broader pedagogical framework and may be less immediately associated with external scrutiny. Moreover, existing work suggests that even where changes do occur - such as reductions in cheating or increases in test score validity - the effects of monitoring fade within two years, likely due to the lack of sustained pressure or institutional embedding (Bertoni et al., 2021).

Despite theoretical grounds to expect heterogeneous effects, our analysis does not reveal any significant variation across contexts. For example, we anticipated stronger effects in the South and Center of Italy, regions typically characterized by more generous grading practices (Triventi and Argentin, 2015), lower levels of civic capital (Putnam et al., 1993), and more frequent opportunistic responses to accountability (Paccagnella and Sestito, 2014; Ferrer-Esteban and Pagès, 2024). However, the results show no meaningful differences by geographic area, suggesting that local norms, the perceived legitimacy of evaluation practices, and reputational concerns may not substantially moderate teacher behavior in response to soft accountability.

Similarly, we expected accountability signals to be more salient in larger or higher-SES schools, which tend to be more exposed to external scrutiny (Lucifora and Tonello, 2020). Yet, our analysis did not detect any systematic effects by school size or socioeconomic composition. These null findings suggest that, in practice, soft accountability mechanisms may have limited power to shift behaviors, even in environments theoretically more sensitive to external

evaluation pressures. Deeply institutionalized practices, particularly around grading, appear largely unaffected.

8. Limitations

This study is subject to limitations that should be examined and carefully addressed in future replications. A primary constraint lies in the inability to account for the proportion of tenured teachers during the years under examination. It is plausible that the perceived relevance of the monitoring intervention varied across schools depending on the prevalence of tenured staff. For instance, in school institutes with a higher proportion of tenured teachers, grading practices may be more routinized and resistant to change due to entrenched professional norms. Conversely, such teachers may also be more responsive to symbolic and reputational incentives, which could motivate shifts in grading behavior under external scrutiny.

In the Italian context, tenure is typically acquired after multiple years of annual assignments, often marked by discontinuity and limited institutional affiliation (Barbieri et al., 2010). This structural feature contributes to a high degree of teacher mobility across schools, which may, in turn, dilute the effects of monitoring interventions. The reduced salience of accountability mechanisms might thus offer a potential explanation for the limited impact observed in grading outcomes.

A second limitation concerns the complex nature of grading practices, of which marks represent only a partial manifestation. Grades are the visible outcome of a broader process that encompasses, among other elements, the selection of assessment criteria, the modes through which feedback is communicated to students, and the ways in which evaluative consequences are managed by teachers, students, and families. In this sense, marks constitute one fragment of a broader pedagogical framework, one that is difficult to fully capture through large-scale quantitative assessments.

An additional layer of complexity arises from the diverse meanings that are attributed to grades, which frequently amalgamate multiple factors, including academic achievement, effort, behavior, and perceived improvement (Link and Mitic, 2025). As Brookhart (1991) observed, such “hodgepodge” grades pose interpretive challenges for educational stakeholders seeking to make informed decisions and, as we contend, for researchers attempting to analyze grading outcomes through quantitative methods.

9. Conclusion

Our findings suggest that light-touch accountability measures, such as temporary monitoring in a low-stakes regime, are unlikely to produce meaningful changes in entrenched school-level practices like grading. For accountability to influence such practices, it may require more sustained engagement, professional development around assessment norms, or more structured opportunities for internal deliberation on grading standards (Verger and Parcerisa, 2017; Locke et al., 2005).

From a policy perspective, this has important implications for the design of accountability systems, especially in countries with high grading heterogeneity and low institutional trust. If the goal is to reduce regional disparities in grading standards or improve alignment between grades and competencies, relying solely on symbolic or reputational mechanisms may not be sufficient. Instead, policy efforts should consider how to support internal school dialogue, promote consistent expectations, and enable gradual cultural shifts in evaluation practices.

Finally, our study reinforces the importance of examining school responses beyond test outcomes, by analyzing how accountability tools interact with the everyday routines of teaching. While high-stakes regimes often produce measurable but sometimes problematic responses, low-stakes systems face the opposite challenge: they may foster better trust and collaboration, but struggle to trigger visible change. Future research should continue to explore how different forms of accountability affect not just what schools do, but how they understand and value their role in student development.

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APPENDIX

Table A.1. Pairwise correlations between oral and written marks (Pooled sample).

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1) Italian - Oral	1.000			
(2) Italian - Written	0.969	1.000		
(3) Math - Oral	0.821	0.825	1.000	
(4) Math - Written	0.822	0.833	0.972	1.000

Table A.2. Descriptive statistics of unmonitored and monitored schools (2013).

Variable	Unmonitored	Monitored	Total	Test
N	13187 (92.72%)	1035 (7.28%)	14222 (100%)	
Grades				
Mean - Italian	7.72 (0.52)	7.74 (0.47)	7.72 (0.51)	0.23
Mean - Math	7.80 (0.53)	7.82 (0.49)	7.80 (0.52)	0.42
CV - Italian	0.13 (0.03)	0.13 (0.03)	0.13 (0.03)	0.09
CV - Math	0.13 (0.04)	0.13 (0.04)	0.13 (0.04)	0.46
INVALSI scores				
Mean - Italian	210.78 (23.67)	202.24 (18.48)	210.16 (23.44)	<.001
Mean - Math	213.97 (28.23)	203.21 (22.15)	213.19 (27.98)	<.001
CV - Italian	0.17 (0.04)	0.18 (0.04)	0.17 (0.04)	<.001
CV - Math	0.16 (0.04)	0.18 (0.03)	0.17 (0.04)	<.001
School characteristics				
School size	36.51 (25.11)	48.57 (31.05)	37.39 (25.78)	<.001
Females	0.50 (0.11)	0.50 (0.09)	0.50 (0.11)	0.47
Natives	0.90 (0.12)	0.90 (0.13)	0.90 (0.12)	0.72
School-level ESCS	0.03 (0.53)	0.03 (0.50)	0.03 (0.52)	0.90

Note. Values are means with standard deviations in parentheses. CV = coefficient of variation. ESCS = index of economic, social, and cultural status provided by INVALSI and standardized to a mean of zero. The *Test* column reports *p*-values from *t*-tests comparing monitored and unmonitored schools.

Table A.3. Descriptive statistics of unmonitored and monitored schools (2014).

Variable	Unmonitored	Monitored	Total	Test
N	11808 (92.9%)	902 (7.1%)	12710 (100%)	
Grades				
Mean - Italian	7.76 (0.49)	7.81 (0.47)	7.77 (0.49)	0.01
Mean - Math	7.84 (0.50)	7.87 (0.47)	7.84 (0.50)	0.09

Variable	Unmonitored	Monitored	Total	Test
CV - Italian	0.12 (0.03)	0.12 (0.03)	0.12 (0.03)	0.25
CV - Math	0.13 (0.03)	0.13 (0.03)	0.13 (0.03)	0.17
INVALSI scores				
Mean - Italian	210.34 (23.41)	201.72 (17.51)	209.73 (23.15)	<.001
Mean - Math	210.60 (24.80)	201.85 (17.88)	209.97 (24.47)	<.001
CV - Italian	0.17 (0.05)	0.18 (0.04)	0.17 (0.05)	<.001
CV - Math	0.17 (0.04)	0.18 (0.04)	0.17 (0.04)	<.001
School characteristics				
School size	33.18 (21.88)	43.31 (27.68)	33.90 (22.49)	<.001
Females	0.49 (0.12)	0.49 (0.10)	0.49 (0.12)	0.90
Natives	0.90 (0.12)	0.91 (0.10)	0.90 (0.12)	0.02
School-level ESCS	-0.00 (0.48)	0.07 (0.44)	0.00 (0.47)	<.001

Note. Values are means with standard deviations in parentheses. CV = coefficient of variation. ESCS = index of economic, social, and cultural status provided by INVALSI and standardized to a mean of zero. The *Test* column reports *p*-values from *t*-tests comparing monitored and unmonitored schools.

Figure A.1. High vs Low ESCS schools: the effect of external monitoring on marks.

Figure A.2. High vs Low ESCS schools: the effect of external monitoring on grading standards.

